

Supporting Information

Synthesis and evaluation of biological activities of bis(spiropyrazolone)cyclopropanes: a potential application against leishmaniasis

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Figure S1. Cell morphology of RKO, PC-3 and HeLa cell lines exposed to the Inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) of the most active bis (spiropyrazolone) cyclopropanes for 48 hours. Data are given as mean and standard error (SEM) of at least three independent experiments. Horizontal bar in the figure below = 50 μm .

Figure S2. Representative examples of *Leishmania mexicana* cells exposed to bis(spiropyrazolone)cyclopropanes 4 and subjected to comet assay. C, control unexposed cells; DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide; MMS, methyl methanesulfonate.

Figure S4. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2b**Figure S5. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2c**

Figure S7. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2e**

1H (2f) 2-Ome.esp

Figure S8. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2f**

181_PROTON-3.esp

Figure S9. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2g

Figure S10. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2h

Figure S11. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **2h**

Figure S12. FTIR spectrum of compound **2h**

Monoisotopic Mass, Even Electron Ions
 111 formula(e) evaluated with 4 results within limits (up to 19 closest results for each mass)
 Elements Used:
 C: 0-100 H: 0-200 N: 5-5 O: 0-30
 24-Jun-2016
 jhm-24jun16-203-33 402 (7.435) Cn (Cen,7, 50.00, Ar); Sm (SG, 3x5.00); Sb (12,5.00)

TOF MS ES+
 4.59e+003

Mass	Calc. Mass	mDa	PPM	DBE	i-FIT	Formula
498.1772	498.1777	-0.5	-1.0	18.5	0.8	C27 H24 N5 O5
	498.1719	5.3	10.6	27.5	40.7	C34 H20 N5
	498.1836	-6.4	-12.8	9.5	33.4	C20 H28 N5 O10
	498.1684	8.8	17.7	5.5	92.6	C16 H28 N5 O13

Molecular Formula = C₂₇H₂₃N₅O₅
 [M+H]⁺ = 498.177195 Da

Figure S2. HRMS spectrum of compound 2h

Figure S34. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2i.

JH-203-35 (1H).esp

DMSO-d6

Figure S45. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2j.

1H (2k) 4-NO2.esp

CDCl3

Figure S56. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2k.

1H (2) 3-OH.esp

Figure S67. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2l**.

JH-203-42 (1H).esp

Figure S78. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2m**.

Figure S89. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **2m**

Figure S20. FTIR spectrum of compound **2m**

Monoisotopic Mass, Even Electron Ions
 118 formula(e) evaluated with 4 results within limits (up to 19 closest results for each mass)
 Elements Used:
 C: 0-100 H: 0-200 N: 4-4 O: 0-30
 24-Jun-2016
 jhm-24jun16-203-42 167 (3.089) Cn (Cen,7, 50.00, Ar); Sm (SG, 3x5.00); Sb (12.5.00)

TOF MS ES+
 9.57e+003

Mass	Calc. Mass	mDa	PPM	DBE	i-FIT	Formula
513.2136	513.2138	-0.2	-0.4	17.5	539.1	C29 H29 N4 O5
	513.2079	5.7	11.1	26.5	942.9	C36 H25 N4
	513.2197	-6.1	-11.9	8.5	222.9	C22 H33 N4 O10
	513.2044	9.2	17.9	4.5	125.0	C18 H33 N4 O13

Molecular Formula = C₂₉H₂₈N₄O₅
 [M+H]⁺ = 513.213246 Da

Figure S21. HRMS spectrum of compound 2m

1H (2n) 3,4-diOH.esp

Figure S22. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 2n.

1H (2o) 4-OH.esp

Figure S23. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2o**.

1H (2p) 4-F.esp

Figure S24. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2p**.

Figure S25. ^{19}F NMR spectrum of compound **2p**.

Figure S26. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2q**.

1H (2r) 4-CF3.esp

Figure S27. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2r**.

1H (2s) 500 MHz.esp

Figure S28. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2s**.

1H (2t) 3-F.esp

Figure S99. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2t**.

1H (2u) 4-SMe.esp

Figure S30. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **2u**.

4b (JH-213-S1) 1H.esp

Figure S31. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **4b**

4b (JH-213-S1) 13C.esp

Figure S32. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **4b**

Figure S33. FTIR spectrum of compound **4b**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	450 m/z
Accumulation Time	200000 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	174.84	174.93	[M + H] ⁺	3230 100.00
B	435.11	435.30	[M + H] ⁺	1784 55.22
C	262.94	263.10	[M + H] ⁺	521 16.14

Figure S34. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4b**

Figure S37. FTIR spectrum of compound **4c**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	200000 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	502.18	502.66	[M + H] ⁺	150245
B	482.27	482.67	[M + H] ⁺	8078

Figure S108. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4c**

4d (JH-222-S1) 1H.esp

CDCL3

Figure S119. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **4d**

4d (JH-222-S1) 13C.esp

Figure S40. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **4d**

Figure S41. FTIR spectrum of compound **4d**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	XtremeScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	400 m/z
Accumulation Time	20000 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	3 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	172.82	172.90	[M - H] ⁻	7518 100.00
B	480.23	480.77	[M - H] ⁻	2933 39.01

Figure S122. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4d**

Figure S45. FTIR spectrum of compound **4e**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	500 m/z
Accumulation Time	199196 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	174.85	174.92	[M + H] ⁺	100.00
B	292.97	293.12	[M + H] ⁺	59.57
C	465.15	465.53	[M + H] ⁺	6.66

Figure S156. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4e**

Figure S179. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 4k

Figure S50. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound 4k

Figure S51. FTIR spectrum of compound 4k

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	200000 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	502.16	502.49 [M + H] ⁺	11262	100.00

Figure S182. ESI-MS spectrum of compound 4k

Figure S19. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **4p**

Figure S20. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **4p**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	9580 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Figure S57. ESI-MS spectrum of compound 4p

Figure S228. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 4q

Figure S23. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **4q**

Figure S60. FTIR spectrum of compound **4q**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	6959 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	493.30	493.68	[M + H] ⁺	11388026 100.00
B	515.27	515.66	[M + H] ⁺	4469086 39.24
C	1023.56	1024.28	[M + H] ⁺	1620959 14.23
D	593.71	594.37	[M + H] ⁺	771212 6.77
E	577.26	578.08	[M + H] ⁺	758822 6.66

Figure S61. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4q**

Figure S242. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **4r**

13C (4r).esp

Figure S253. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound 4r

4r — Recorded on Oxford Instruments Pulsar —

Figure S264. ^{19}F NMR spectrum of compound 4r

Figure S275. FTIR spectrum of compound **4r**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	13368 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	503.36	503.75	[M + H] ⁺	2206733
B	525.32	525.72	[M + H] ⁺	1378402
C	413.47	413.97	[M + H] ⁺	356961
D	301.28	301.90	[M + H] ⁺	294262

Figure S286. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4r**

Figure S297. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 4s

Figure S68. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **4s**

4s — Recorded on Oxford Instruments Pulsar —

Figure S69. ^{19}F NMR spectrum of compound **4s**

Figure S70. FTIR spectrum of compound **4s**

13C (4t).esp

Figure S313. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **4t**

4t — Recorded on Oxford Instruments Pulsar —

Figure S324. ¹⁹F NMR spectrum of compound **4t**

Figure S335. FTIR spectrum of compound **4t**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	200000 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	475.19	475.53	[M + H] ⁺	88901
B	453.24	453.65	[M + H] ⁺	37933

Figure S346. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4t**

Figure S357. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **4u**

Figure S368. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **4u**

Figure S379. FTIR spectrum of compound **4u**

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	200000 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	503.20	503.63	[M + H] ⁺	49718
B	481.23	481.71	[M + H] ⁺	3790

Figure S80. ESI-MS spectrum of compound **4u**

5g 1H (CDCl3).esp

Figure S381. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **5g**

1H (4).esp

Figure S392. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 6

Figure S403. ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound 6

Figure S414. DEPT spectrum of compound 6

Figure S425. HSQC spectrum of compound 6

Figure S86. HMBC spectrum of compound 6

Figure S437. FTIR spectrum of compound 6

Acquisition Parameter

Ion Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Alternating Ion Polarity	off
Mass Range Mode	UltraScan	Scan Begin	70 m/z	Scan End	600 m/z
Accumulation Time	200000 μ s	RF Level	63 %	Trap Drive	54.1
SPS Target Mass	400 m/z	Averages	5 Spectra	n/a	n/a

Component	Molecular Mass	Molecule	Absolute Abundance	Relative Abundance
A	381.15	381.42	[M + H] ⁺	27417
B	359.19	359.55	[M + H] ⁺	2350

Figure S448. ESI-MS spectrum of compound 6

Table S1. Percentage (%) of inhibition of five human cancer cell lines, and immortalized cell CHO K-1 exposed 48 h to 100 μM of each bis(spiropyrazolone)cyclopropanes **4**.

	RKO	PC-3	A-549	MCF-7	HeLa	CHO-K1
4b	21.74 $\pm$ 2.37	17.56 $\pm$ 2.83	NA	7.87 $\pm$ 2.92	NA	5.76 $\pm$ 3.08
4c	37.29 $\pm$ 1.22	11.03 $\pm$ 3.50	6.10 $\pm$ 0.86	16.69 $\pm$ 5.36	24.80 $\pm$ 1.74	2.62 $\pm$ 2.20
4d	68.88 $\pm$ 1.72	46.08 $\pm$ 1.91	13.64 $\pm$ 0.74	39.41 $\pm$ 2.29	48.56 $\pm$ 4.91	4.40 $\pm$ 0.72
4e	36.77 $\pm$ 1.55	17.93 $\pm$ 3.40	7.97 $\pm$ 1.46	4.47 $\pm$ 3.48	47.84 $\pm$ 2.45	NA
4f	28.74 $\pm$ 0.29	28.32 $\pm$ 2.56	10.36 $\pm$ 3.28	NA	NA	2.79 $\pm$ 1.49
4k	67.59 $\pm$ 0.77	46.72 $\pm$ 3.78	26.71 $\pm$ 3.03	43.03 $\pm$ 3.46	47.22 $\pm$ 1.36	NA
4p	18.59 $\pm$ 1.37	5.25 $\pm$ 2.60	9.08 $\pm$ 1.14	13.64 $\pm$ 2.55	5.98 $\pm$ 2.19	1.95 $\pm$ 1.42
4q	62.87 $\pm$ 1.53	50.51 $\pm$ 2.38	13.00 $\pm$ 1.99	32.48 $\pm$ 2.33	31.72 $\pm$ 1.52	2.29 $\pm$ 2.60
4r	64.71 $\pm$ 0.52	54.66 $\pm$ 1.95	28.65 $\pm$ 3.71	45.75 $\pm$ 2.11	50.16 $\pm$ 0.52	4.74 $\pm$ 3.04
4s	70.23 $\pm$ 1.19	49.74 $\pm$ 2.11	24.42 $\pm$ 1.36	9.91 $\pm$ 3.37	43.56 $\pm$ 1.75	NA
4t	47.57 $\pm$ 0.95	13.81 $\pm$ 2.87	3.43 $\pm$ 2.42	31.41 $\pm$ 3.65	5.06 $\pm$ 2.43	5.08 $\pm$ 2.84
4u	40.96 $\pm$ 1.49	38.68 $\pm$ 3.77	3.64 $\pm$ 1.81	19.51 $\pm$ 2.96	34.73 $\pm$ 2.29	5.76 $\pm$ 3.65
Dox	85.63 $\pm$ 1.06	87.98 $\pm$ 1.65	9.16 $\pm$ 2.16	46.23 $\pm$ 7.77	9.18 $\pm$ 9.55	2.62 $\pm$ 1.42

Data are given as mean and standard error (SEM) of at least three independent experiments; NA: No activity; Dox: Doxorubicin (1 μM).

Table S2. DPPH scavenging activity of bis(spiropyrazolone)cyclopropanes **4**.

	DPPH scavenging activity IC₅₀ μM
4b	> 300
4c	> 300
4d	> 300
4e	> 300
4f	> 300
4k	233.8
4p	> 300
4q	> 300
4r	> 300
4s	> 300
4t	> 300
4u	> 300
Ascorbic acid	14.0
Ampho B	ND

Statistical Analyses S1. Kruskal Wallis test's applied to comet assay of *Leishmania mexicana* cells exposed to bis(spiropyrazolone)cyclopropanes 4 (Figure 2).

Study: Trat
 Kruskal-Wallis test's
 Ties or no Ties

Critical Value: 1004.543
 Degrees of freedom: 13
 Pvalue Chisq : 0

trat, means of the ranks

trat	mean	r
C.	97.280	100
DMSO.	207.115	100
MMS.	606.840	100
X4b	449.315	100
X4c	648.065	100
X4d	694.660	100
X4e	595.490	100
X4f	691.135	100
X4k	1111.660	100
X4q	1208.625	80
X4r	861.180	100
X4s	352.245	100
X4t	1016.210	100
X4u	1230.805	100

Post Hoc Analysis

P value adjustment method: bonferroni

t-Student: 3.463614

Alpha : 0.05

Groups according to probability of treatment differences and alpha level.

Treatments with the same letter are not significantly different.

```
vary groups
X4u 1230.805  a
X4q 1208.625  ab
X4k 1111.660  bc
X4t 1016.210  c
X4r  861.180  d
X4d  694.660  e
X4f  691.135  e
X4c  648.065  e
MMS. 606.840  e
X4e  595.490  e
X4b  449.315  f
X4s  352.245  f
DMSO. 207.115  g
C.    97.280   h
```

\$statistics

```
Chisq Df p.chisq
1004.543 13 0
```

\$parameters

```
test p.adjusted name.t ntr alpha
Kruskal-Wallis bonferroni trat 14 0.05
```

\$means

```
vary rank std r Min Max Q25 Q50 Q75
C. 10290000 97.280 9224796 100 0.0e+00 4.80e+07 4000000 8000000 14000000
DMSO. 23610000 207.115 14071890 100 0.0e+00 5.50e+07 11000000 25000000 35000000
MMS. 67050000 606.840 16924894 100 0.0e+00 1.16e+08 58000000 65000000 74250000
X4b 50400000 449.315 20682301 100 2.0e+06 8.90e+07 32750000 55000000 64000000
X4c 70710000 648.065 18193847 100 1.4e+07 1.11e+08 58750000 72500000 83250000
X4d 75120000 694.660 29056295 100 0.0e+00 1.21e+08 52000000 83500000 97250000
X4e 65120000 595.490 29979549 100 7.0e+06 1.23e+08 39750000 64500000 90250000
X4f 75100000 691.135 28784641 100 1.1e+07 1.49e+08 55000000 80500000 99000000
X4k 142780000 1111.660 45723716 100 6.3e+07 2.48e+08 110000000 128000000 182500000
X4q 172025000 1208.625 46560965 80 7.5e+07 2.59e+08 129750000 177500000 205750000
X4r 96310000 861.180 33823277 100 2.3e+07 1.68e+08 76500000 98500000 117500000
X4s 39720000 352.245 22688528 100 0.0e+00 9.10e+07 23000000 39500000 55250000
X4t 124410000 1016.210 44002317 100 4.0e+06 2.09e+08 95250000 116000000 157000000
X4u 179560000 1230.805 48875087 100 8.7e+07 2.79e+08 142000000 177500000 223000000
```

\$comparison

	Difference	pvalue	Signif.	LCL	UCL
C. - DMSO.	-109.835	0.0187	*	-212.036162	-7.633838
C. - MMS.	-509.560	0.0000	***	-611.761162	-407.358838
C. - X4b	-352.035	0.0000	***	-454.236162	-249.833838
C. - X4c	-550.785	0.0000	***	-652.986162	-448.583838
C. - X4d	-597.380	0.0000	***	-699.581162	-495.178838
C. - X4e	-498.210	0.0000	***	-600.411162	-396.008838
C. - X4f	-593.855	0.0000	***	-696.056162	-491.653838
C. - X4k	-1014.380	0.0000	***	-1116.581162	-912.178838
C. - X4q	-1111.345	0.0000	***	-1219.745702	-1002.944298
C. - X4r	-763.900	0.0000	***	-866.101162	-661.698838
C. - X4s	-254.965	0.0000	***	-357.166162	-152.763838
C. - X4t	-918.930	0.0000	***	-1021.131162	-816.728838
C. - X4u	-1133.525	0.0000	***	-1235.726162	-1031.323838
DMSO. - MMS.	-399.725	0.0000	***	-501.926162	-297.523838
DMSO. - X4b	-242.200	0.0000	***	-344.401162	-139.998838
DMSO. - X4c	-440.950	0.0000	***	-543.151162	-338.748838
DMSO. - X4d	-487.545	0.0000	***	-589.746162	-385.343838
DMSO. - X4e	-388.375	0.0000	***	-490.576162	-286.173838
DMSO. - X4f	-484.020	0.0000	***	-586.221162	-381.818838
DMSO. - X4k	-904.545	0.0000	***	-1006.746162	-802.343838
DMSO. - X4q	-1001.510	0.0000	***	-1109.910702	-893.109298
DMSO. - X4r	-654.065	0.0000	***	-756.266162	-551.863838
DMSO. - X4s	-145.130	0.0001	***	-247.331162	-42.928838
DMSO. - X4t	-809.095	0.0000	***	-911.296162	-706.893838
DMSO. - X4u	-1023.690	0.0000	***	-1125.891162	-921.488838
MMS. - X4b	157.525	0.0000	***	55.323838	259.726162
MMS. - X4c	-41.225	1.0000		-143.426162	60.976162
MMS. - X4d	-87.820	0.2702		-190.021162	14.381162
MMS. - X4e	11.350	1.0000		-90.851162	113.551162
MMS. - X4f	-84.295	0.3954		-186.496162	17.906162
MMS. - X4k	-504.820	0.0000	***	-607.021162	-402.618838
MMS. - X4q	-601.785	0.0000	***	-710.185702	-493.384298
MMS. - X4r	-254.340	0.0000	***	-356.541162	-152.138838
MMS. - X4s	254.595	0.0000	***	152.393838	356.796162
MMS. - X4t	-409.370	0.0000	***	-511.571162	-307.168838
MMS. - X4u	-623.965	0.0000	***	-726.166162	-521.763838
X4b - X4c	-198.750	0.0000	***	-300.951162	-96.548838
X4b - X4d	-245.345	0.0000	***	-347.546162	-143.143838
X4b - X4e	-146.175	0.0001	***	-248.376162	-43.973838
X4b - X4f	-241.820	0.0000	***	-344.021162	-139.618838
X4b - X4k	-662.345	0.0000	***	-764.546162	-560.143838
X4b - X4q	-759.310	0.0000	***	-867.710702	-650.909298
X4b - X4r	-411.865	0.0000	***	-514.066162	-309.663838
X4b - X4s	97.070	0.0936	.	-5.131162	199.271162
X4b - X4t	-566.895	0.0000	***	-669.096162	-464.693838
X4b - X4u	-781.490	0.0000	***	-883.691162	-679.288838
X4c - X4d	-46.595	1.0000		-148.796162	55.606162
X4c - X4e	52.575	1.0000		-49.626162	154.776162
X4c - X4f	-43.070	1.0000		-145.271162	59.131162
X4c - X4k	-463.595	0.0000	***	-565.796162	-361.393838

X4c - X4q	-560.560 0.0000	***	-668.960702	-452.159298
X4c - X4r	-213.115 0.0000	***	-315.316162	-110.913838
X4c - X4s	295.820 0.0000	***	193.618838	398.021162
X4c - X4t	-368.145 0.0000	***	-470.346162	-265.943838
X4c - X4u	-582.740 0.0000	***	-684.941162	-480.538838
X4d - X4e	99.170 0.0727	.	-3.031162	201.371162
X4d - X4f	3.525 1.0000		-98.676162	105.726162
X4d - X4k	-417.000 0.0000	***	-519.201162	-314.798838
X4d - X4q	-513.965 0.0000	***	-622.365702	-405.564298
X4d - X4r	-166.520 0.0000	***	-268.721162	-64.318838
X4d - X4s	342.415 0.0000	***	240.213838	444.616162
X4d - X4t	-321.550 0.0000	***	-423.751162	-219.348838
X4d - X4u	-536.145 0.0000	***	-638.346162	-433.943838
X4e - X4f	-95.645 0.1108		-197.846162	6.556162
X4e - X4k	-516.170 0.0000	***	-618.371162	-413.968838
X4e - X4q	-613.135 0.0000	***	-721.535702	-504.734298
X4e - X4r	-265.690 0.0000	***	-367.891162	-163.488838
X4e - X4s	243.245 0.0000	***	141.043838	345.446162
X4e - X4t	-420.720 0.0000	***	-522.921162	-318.518838
X4e - X4u	-635.315 0.0000	***	-737.516162	-533.113838
X4f - X4k	-420.525 0.0000	***	-522.726162	-318.323838
X4f - X4q	-517.490 0.0000	***	-625.890702	-409.089298
X4f - X4r	-170.045 0.0000	***	-272.246162	-67.843838
X4f - X4s	338.890 0.0000	***	236.688838	441.091162
X4f - X4t	-325.075 0.0000	***	-427.276162	-222.873838
X4f - X4u	-539.670 0.0000	***	-641.871162	-437.468838
X4k - X4q	-96.965 0.1808		-205.365702	11.435702
X4k - X4r	250.480 0.0000	***	148.278838	352.681162
X4k - X4s	759.415 0.0000	***	657.213838	861.616162
X4k - X4t	95.450 0.1134		-6.751162	197.651162
X4k - X4u	-119.145 0.0052	**	-221.346162	-16.943838
X4q - X4r	347.445 0.0000	***	239.044298	455.845702
X4q - X4s	856.380 0.0000	***	747.979298	964.780702
X4q - X4t	192.415 0.0000	***	84.014298	300.815702
X4q - X4u	-22.180 1.0000		-130.580702	86.220702
X4r - X4s	508.935 0.0000	***	406.733838	611.136162
X4r - X4t	-155.030 0.0000	***	-257.231162	-52.828838
X4r - X4u	-369.625 0.0000	***	-471.826162	-267.423838
X4s - X4t	-663.965 0.0000	***	-766.166162	-561.763838
X4s - X4u	-878.560 0.0000	***	-980.761162	-776.358838
X4t - X4u	-214.595 0.0000	***	-316.796162	-112.393838

Statistical Analyses S2. Kruskal Wallis test's applied to comet assay of CHO cells exposed to bis(spiropyrazolone)cyclopropanes 4 (Figure 3).

\$statistics

```
Chisq Df p.chisq t.value  MSD
1708.307 13 0 1.960247 245.1376
```

\$parameters

```
test p.adjusted name.t ntr alpha
Kruskal-Wallis none trat 14 0.05
```

\$means

	vary	rank	std	r	Min	Max	Q25	Q50	Q75
DMSO	66045840	3568.301	27896533	600	23429540.0	166553500	42784380	57045840	89134120
Dox	209447368	7865.864	51979579	600	19864180.0	396264900	183361600	217996600	240916800
X4b	61401527	3115.134	28639223	600	509337.8	246519500	45331070	53989810	65195240
X4c	76526316	4376.037	35814130	600	24957560.0	260781000	52843805	62648560	92954160
X4d	78343803	4521.320	34892342	600	23429540.0	235314100	52461800	65704580	95755520
X4e	71876061	4164.706	29613974	600	31069610.0	197113800	51443120	61120540	82640065
X4f	72036501	4055.789	32998506	600	18845500.0	215449900	49915110	61629880	83022070
X4k	74173175	4427.186	31543285	600	25976230.0	217487300	55008490	63667230	80093375
X4p	68013582	3946.407	27613069	600	27504240.0	232767400	51825125	60101870	71816640
X4q	65551784	3537.702	28621584	600	18336160.0	296944000	43293720	56791170	86714765
X4r	72132428	4106.395	29902529	600	27504240.0	246010200	48896430	61629880	94736840
X4s	68389643	4118.727	25773413	600	25976230.0	232258100	52971140	62648560	73344650
X4t	61194397	3386.662	20212790	600	26485570.0	198132400	46859090	57045840	69779290
X4u	64116299	3616.770	23301875	600	28013580.0	209337900	47877760	58573850	72325970

\$comparison

NULL

\$groups

vary groups

Dox	7865.864	a
X4d	4521.320	b
X4k	4427.186	b
X4c	4376.037	bc
X4e	4164.706	cd
X4s	4118.727	d
X4r	4106.395	d
X4f	4055.789	d
X4p	3946.407	d
X4u	3616.770	e
DMSO	3568.301	e
X4q	3537.702	e
X4t	3386.662	e
X4b	3115.134	f

\$statistics

Chisq	Df	p.chisq	t.value	MSD
1708.307	13	0	3.456746	432.2815

\$parameters

test	p.adjusted	name.t	ntr	alpha
Kruskal-Wallis	bonferroni	trat	14	0.05

\$means

vary	rank	std	r	Min	Max	Q25	Q50	Q75	
DMSO	66045840	3568.301	27896533	600	23429540.0	166553500	42784380	57045840	89134120
Dox	209447368	7865.864	51979579	600	19864180.0	396264900	183361600	217996600	240916800
X4b	61401527	3115.134	28639223	600	509337.8	246519500	45331070	53989810	65195240
X4c	76526316	4376.037	35814130	600	24957560.0	260781000	52843805	62648560	92954160
X4d	78343803	4521.320	34892342	600	23429540.0	235314100	52461800	65704580	95755520
X4e	71876061	4164.706	29613974	600	31069610.0	197113800	51443120	61120540	82640065
X4f	72036501	4055.789	32998506	600	18845500.0	215449900	49915110	61629880	83022070
X4k	74173175	4427.186	31543285	600	25976230.0	217487300	55008490	63667230	80093375
X4p	68013582	3946.407	27613069	600	27504240.0	232767400	51825125	60101870	71816640
X4q	65551784	3537.702	28621584	600	18336160.0	296944000	43293720	56791170	86714765
X4r	72132428	4106.395	29902529	600	27504240.0	246010200	48896430	61629880	94736840
X4s	68389643	4118.727	25773413	600	25976230.0	232258100	52971140	62648560	73344650
X4t	61194397	3386.662	20212790	600	26485570.0	198132400	46859090	57045840	69779290
X4u	64116299	3616.770	23301875	600	28013580.0	209337900	47877760	58573850	72325970

\$comparison

	Difference	pvalue	Signif.	LCL	UCL
DMSO - Dox	-4297.56333	0.0000	***	-4729.844865	-3865.281801
DMSO - X4b	453.16667	0.0266	*	20.885135	885.448199
DMSO - X4c	-807.73583	0.0000	***	-1240.017365	-375.454301
DMSO - X4d	-953.01917	0.0000	***	-1385.300699	-520.737635
DMSO - X4e	-596.40500	0.0002	***	-1028.686532	-164.123468
DMSO - X4f	-487.48833	0.0089	**	-919.769865	-55.206801

DMSO - X4k	-858.88500	0.0000	***	-1291.166532	-426.603468
DMSO - X4p	-378.10583	0.2280		-810.387365	54.175699
DMSO - X4q	30.59917	1.0000		-401.682365	462.880699
DMSO - X4r	-538.09417	0.0016	**	-970.375699	-105.812635
DMSO - X4s	-550.42667	0.0010	***	-982.708199	-118.145135
DMSO - X4t	181.63833	1.0000		-250.643199	613.919865
DMSO - X4u	-48.46917	1.0000		-480.750699	383.812365
Dox - X4b	4750.73000	0.0000	***	4318.448468	5183.011532
Dox - X4c	3489.82750	0.0000	***	3057.545968	3922.109032
Dox - X4d	3344.54417	0.0000	***	2912.262635	3776.825699
Dox - X4e	3701.15833	0.0000	***	3268.876801	4133.439865
Dox - X4f	3810.07500	0.0000	***	3377.793468	4242.356532
Dox - X4k	3438.67833	0.0000	***	3006.396801	3870.959865
Dox - X4p	3919.45750	0.0000	***	3487.175968	4351.739032
Dox - X4q	4328.16250	0.0000	***	3895.880968	4760.444032
Dox - X4r	3759.46917	0.0000	***	3327.187635	4191.750699
Dox - X4s	3747.13667	0.0000	***	3314.855135	4179.418199
Dox - X4t	4479.20167	0.0000	***	4046.920135	4911.483199
Dox - X4u	4249.09417	0.0000	***	3816.812635	4681.375699
X4b - X4c	-1260.90250	0.0000	***	-1693.184032	-828.620968
X4b - X4d	-1406.18583	0.0000	***	-1838.467365	-973.904301
X4b - X4e	-1049.57167	0.0000	***	-1481.853199	-617.290135
X4b - X4f	-940.65500	0.0000	***	-1372.936532	-508.373468
X4b - X4k	-1312.05167	0.0000	***	-1744.333199	-879.770135
X4b - X4p	-831.27250	0.0000	***	-1263.554032	-398.990968
X4b - X4q	-422.56750	0.0665	.	-854.849032	9.714032
X4b - X4r	-991.26083	0.0000	***	-1423.542365	-558.979301
X4b - X4s	-1003.59333	0.0000	***	-1435.874865	-571.311801
X4b - X4t	-271.52833	1.0000		-703.809865	160.753199
X4b - X4u	-501.63583	0.0055	**	-933.917365	-69.354301
X4c - X4d	-145.28333	1.0000		-577.564865	286.998199
X4c - X4e	211.33083	1.0000		-220.950699	643.612365
X4c - X4f	320.24750	0.9517		-112.034032	752.529032
X4c - X4k	-51.14917	1.0000		-483.430699	381.132365
X4c - X4p	429.63000	0.0541	.	-2.651532	861.911532
X4c - X4q	838.33500	0.0000	***	406.053468	1270.616532
X4c - X4r	269.64167	1.0000		-162.639865	701.923199
X4c - X4s	257.30917	1.0000		-174.972365	689.590699
X4c - X4t	989.37417	0.0000	***	557.092635	1421.655699
X4c - X4u	759.26667	0.0000	***	326.985135	1191.548199
X4d - X4e	356.61417	0.3967		-75.667365	788.895699
X4d - X4f	465.53083	0.0181	*	33.249301	897.812365
X4d - X4k	94.13417	1.0000		-338.147365	526.415699
X4d - X4p	574.91333	0.0004	***	142.631801	1007.194865
X4d - X4q	983.61833	0.0000	***	551.336801	1415.899865
X4d - X4r	414.92500	0.0829	.	-17.356532	847.206532
X4d - X4s	402.59250	0.1174		-29.689032	834.874032
X4d - X4t	1134.65750	0.0000	***	702.375968	1566.939032
X4d - X4u	904.55000	0.0000	***	472.268468	1336.831532
X4e - X4f	108.91667	1.0000		-323.364865	541.198199
X4e - X4k	-262.48000	1.0000		-694.761532	169.801532

X4e - X4p	218.29917	1.0000		-213.982365	650.580699
X4e - X4q	627.00417	0.0000	***	194.722635	1059.285699
X4e - X4r	58.31083	1.0000		-373.970699	490.592365
X4e - X4s	45.97833	1.0000		-386.303199	478.259865
X4e - X4t	778.04333	0.0000	***	345.761801	1210.324865
X4e - X4u	547.93583	0.0011	**	115.654301	980.217365
X4f - X4k	-371.39667	0.2719		-803.678199	60.884865
X4f - X4p	109.38250	1.0000		-322.899032	541.664032
X4f - X4q	518.08750	0.0032	**	85.805968	950.369032
X4f - X4r	-50.60583	1.0000		-482.887365	381.675699
X4f - X4s	-62.93833	1.0000		-495.219865	369.343199
X4f - X4t	669.12667	0.0000	***	236.845135	1101.408199
X4f - X4u	439.01917	0.0409	*	6.737635	871.300699
X4k - X4p	480.77917	0.0111	*	48.497635	913.060699
X4k - X4q	889.48417	0.0000	***	457.202635	1321.765699
X4k - X4r	320.79083	0.9399		-111.490699	753.072365
X4k - X4s	308.45833	1.0000		-123.823199	740.739865
X4k - X4t	1040.52333	0.0000	***	608.241801	1472.804865
X4k - X4u	810.41583	0.0000	***	378.134301	1242.697365
X4p - X4q	408.70500	0.0989	.	-23.576532	840.986532
X4p - X4r	-159.98833	1.0000		-592.269865	272.293199
X4p - X4s	-172.32083	1.0000		-604.602365	259.960699
X4p - X4t	559.74417	0.0007	***	127.462635	992.025699
X4p - X4u	329.63667	0.7649		-102.644865	761.918199
X4q - X4r	-568.69333	0.0005	***	-1000.974865	-136.411801
X4q - X4s	-581.02583	0.0003	***	-1013.307365	-148.744301
X4q - X4t	151.03917	1.0000		-281.242365	583.320699
X4q - X4u	-79.06833	1.0000		-511.349865	353.213199
X4r - X4s	-12.33250	1.0000		-444.614032	419.949032
X4r - X4t	719.73250	0.0000	***	287.450968	1152.014032
X4r - X4u	489.62500	0.0083	**	57.343468	921.906532
X4s - X4t	732.06500	0.0000	***	299.783468	1164.346532
X4s - X4u	501.95750	0.0055	**	69.675968	934.239032
X4t - X4u	-230.10750	1.0000		-662.389032	202.174032

\$groups

NULL